

Pfc. Brian Paul Kaess in the U.S. Army at Fort Belvoir, Virginia during the Cold War
by Brian Paul Kaess

From about early March 1986 to August or September 1987, Pfc. Brian Paul Kaess served in the 438th Medical Detachment at Fort Belvoir, Virginia. This was during the Era of the Cold War, when Ronald Reagan was President, and the Soviet Union was in decline. The 438th's sister unit was the 15th Evac Hospital (a company sized element) which also had administrative control of the 438th, which was basically a 12-man unit, run by an Army Medic NCO. The 15th Evac had been famous during WWII as the unit where the 'slapping' incident with Gen. George S. Patton occurred. Because of its distinguished service during WWII, we were allowed to wear a unit citation. Our unit motto was 'Evacuare!' and that was a frequent greeting or 'catcall' of a certain black Master Sgt., who patrolled the barracks.

I had arrived at the unit as a 'mosquito wings' or private and quickly progressed to private first class which was my staple rank for most of my time at Belvoir. One Army Sgt. marveled at the fact that a private like myself had jump wings, which cracked me up. My future wife Ellen Byrd Elliott was an Army Specialist-Four and was an O.R. technician with the 15th Evac.

The 438th went to the field quite a bit for 'commitments' and the 15th Evac went rarely (like once or twice a year)- When I arrived, the 438th had just returned from a deployment to Europe during annual Reforger exercises, and the 15th Evac has been involved in an incident where it had rendered life-saving aid after a plane crash during icy conditions in the Potomac River near Washington National Airport in 1982.

The 438th was composed entirely of combat or field medics and the 15th Evac ran the whole spectrum of what you might expect in a MASH-style unit, from doctors to nurses and specialist enlisted personnel. These personnel were constantly being assigned or rotated to the local Dewitt Army Community Hospital at Fort Belvoir, for clinical training, and the 438th sent our people there as well for three months at a time. We drove M1010 truck ambulances (with a red cross on each side), as well as one older model truck ambulance from a bygone era. The M1010's had push button air conditioning, power steering, and two cushioned racks in the back for patients. More cushion for the pushin'! Two medics were assigned to each vehicle, with multiple commitments daily for our unit. Wooden drew up the board and handed out the work detail and daily start times. Hours could be long, especially during field exercises.

The 5th Evac compound & 438th 'shack' were nearby each other as well as adjacent to a motor pool of truck mechanics. In our enlisted barracks, there were also enlisted helicopter mechanics (wop-wop wings) and MP's. We were under the 4th Engineer Brigade and basically supported Combat Engineers and their operations.

When I first arrived, SFC Fischer, an Airborne veteran, was our NCOIC, and he thought it must have been strange when I asked him if it would be ok if I could take college classes. He initially answered me 'no' but then I found out later night classes would be ok, if the unit authorized it. SSG Wooden thereafter took over, and her and Cpl. Roy (from Philly) were like 'two peas in a pod' enforcing discipline on the 438th soldiers.

The first time I arrived in my barracks room, two other soldiers (man and woman) entered and started having sex, believing I was asleep. Haw! Also, one time, my roommate Dejarmin (a Swedish-American who was married) just had sex with some middle-eastern Army chick, and he left, and she thereafter warmed up to me, cozying up, and flipping through the pages of a girly mag right next to me. But Dejarmin returned in time to reclaim his girl! Dejarmin had done a good job of feeding me while I waited for 'seperate rations' pay to 'kick in.' I met Ellen when she walked up the steps of the 15th Evac Hospital barracks and introduced herself to me, while she was holding her daughter Heather's hand. She was wearing a nice white dress. We began talking and it went from there.

We thereafter dated, I moved in, and then a wedding date was set for June/July. My brother Garret flew in to Washington National Airport for the wedding. ' I explicitly remember cruising along a road near the Potomac River quickly heading north, in haste to pick him up. It was a miracle I was able to locate him in the crowded hall, like a 'needle in a haystack.' But he was disappointed when Ellen called off the wedding, with Garret stating, 'Come on, you're kidding, right!?' I guess she had cold feet. This all changed months later when I told Ellen I was putting myself in for orders overseas, and she decided to 'snatch up a young thing' and went ahead and wanted to get married again. SSG Wooden gave me the lunch hour off one day and told me gleefully, 'Don't you want to go get married to Ellen?!' We 'walked down the aisle' at the Alexandria, Virginia Courthouse in the presence of an 'old hickory' justice of the peace, and as Springsteen once sang: 'the judge put it all to rest!' It was a civil ceremony on a pleasant afternoon. We had married on her daughter Heather's birthday: October 10, 1986. I was 18 years old, just shy of 19.

My buddies were Mills, Tim Walker (from Virginia Beach), Black (a white dude who digged Confederate Heritage), Riddick (from Chicago), Bey (a Rush grad), Dejarmin, Hernandez (from NYC), Niles Arrington (former Ranger from Markham, Illinois), Moton (from Chicago), Helgenson, Vern, Mitchell (dropout from Language School in Monterrey), Garrett (from Barbados), Tracy, Johnson (an MSU grad), Odoms, his wife, another Specialist-4 Odoms, & Anthony 'Tony' Smith (from L.A.), who liked me because I was 'gung-ho.' There was also John, a Medic SSG, who had served in the Vietnam War years before. Mills and Walker, two black soldiers, told me they had served in Europe, and recognizing my name was German, encouraged me to visit Germany someday. I vowed to do just that, but after the Army. There were a couple of hot black chicks in the unit, but I never got around to tagging them 'cause of Ellen, plus one was already married.

They were forced to live in a 'pup tent' in front of the company office as a sort of punishment for sloppy living. Mills had once 'put' me out after I poured gasoline into a carbtorator on an engine we were trying to start and the diesel fuel ignited and exploded, sending me running like a 'flaming torch' for 30-40 feet. The ensuing explosion was witnessed by a neighboring morning formation in the motor pool and that must have been a sight to behold! My friend Mill put me out and I suffered burns on my right arm and forehead, but they healed pretty quickly. My wife Ellen was happy I was ok. She almost collected the military insurance right then and there!

My friend Bob Gillis' dad Winifred Gillis, a former Marine, came out to see me at Fort Belvoir in, I think, 1987, and he waited in the enlisted barracks parking lot literally for days, while the 1st Sgt. passed a message to me in the field that 'your friend Win is here,' and I managed to pull up beside him in the parking lot in our medic vehicle after the exercise and chat for a few minutes. Win caught me being busy with Army life at that particular moment.

There was another time Mills dared me to walk a 'high beam' over a 50-foot drop and we both did so, and an observing Army Lieutenant ran across as well. The chances we take! Another time, a West Point cadet and myself skipped across the bay in an Army boat, similar to a speed boat, and it would have taken just a turn of the wheel to throw us both in the water at such high speeds as we plowed through the oncoming waves- not much room for error!

I was also involved in nighttime 'blackout' drive bridging exercises across the bay, 52 Delta AIT field exercises, Air Assault School (at Davison Army Airfield), Army Engineer BNCOC, ANCOG, Combat Engineer OBC, Quantico, Demolition exercises, field exercises at Ft. A.P. Hill, Expert Field Medical badge (EFMB) test at Fort Meade, Maryland, visited Walter Reed Medical Center ('Walter Wonderful!') in the D.C. area, as well as exercises at Manassas National Battlefield Park, and supporting the 'Old Guard' and other Military District of Washington (MDW) elements. Mills, Walker and I once visited the Vietnam National Memorial, and Niles Arrington and I took a photo in front of the White House. We also saw Arlington National Cemetery and watched the changing of the Guard.

One time we rescued some 2nd Lieutenants who were looking for a ride during a land navigation exercise and cruised them back to their objective in a hurry. I'll always remember them waving! Another time, an Army Lieutenant had set a wooden tree stump on an explosive charge during a demo exercise, and I had just stepped away from the front of my vehicle when the explosion went off, sending the log over the safety burm and heading in my direction, where it struck the front right head light of my medic vehicle, where I had just been standing. Must have felt like I had nine lives and just used one of them!

Often large plumes of dirt would rise into the air quickly after demolition explosions at the range, and after they set the charges, Engineer soldiers would quickly hurry behind bunkers for cover, sometimes smiling as they ran. The window on my vehicle would also shake after each blast, even if I was parked hundreds of meters away!

There was another time, during a 52 Delta AIT exercise, when three older AIT soldiers (former Airborne) almost tried to overpower me and tie me to a tree or something, but another cadre intervened and saved my neck! On one occasion, we held a MOUT or Urban warfare exercise in a mock city or town and the combat engineers did a wonderful job of rolling in from the flank with machine guns (advancing through the tree line), and there were also holdouts in a basement who caused significant casualties, before they were overwhelmed. I observed this all from the top of one of the buildings, having a sort of 'Bird's-Eye-View' of the action. Then

there were also the swooping low of the Apache helicopters near the water during Engineer exercises. Fun stuff!

One time, during a 52 Delta AIT field exercise, I acted as cadre and, at night, behaved like a trainee and walked right through the front gate of the security perimeter undetected and proceeded to 'unload' blank rounds or bursts at the center of the compound, thereafter escaping into the woods, laughing as I went! We also had fun 'ambushing' AIT students as cadre who set up and deployed Claymore Mine simulators. Light 'em up!

On another occasion, the military police brought me over and offered to allow me to shoot two 100-round belts off of an M-60 machine gun on a target range at Belvoir. Since I was a medic and a holder of a Geneva Convention Card, I was not allowed to fire anything such as a machine gun, but I ignored this prohibition and 'blazed away', improving in my accuracy on my 2nd belt. Rambo would have been proud!

One instance, I was sitting in the 438th 'shack' with a bunch of other soldiers of the detachment during the day. SP/4 Riddick came up to me and sort of posed in front of me in a threatening fashion. I thereafter kicked him in the groin and this infuriated him so much that he hauled off and started choking me as if my life depended on breaking his grip. It took half the detachment that was present in the room to pull him off of me. Walker kept trying to loosen Riddick's grip, saying almost patiently, 'Riddick, Riddick, come on, come on!' Eventually, the combined efforts of Walker and the group prevailed and Riddick backed off. It came as a shocker because I always looked up to Riddick as a sort of 'father figure' and I only expected a 'play fight' to ensue, not a full-scale brawl! SSG Wooden seemed amused by the incident and kept jawling away, 'What happened?' Amazingly, no disciplinary action ensued.

Ellen and I lived in the enlisted family housing area at Fort Belvoir, Virginia, with her two kids Steven Ray Ellsberry and Heather Marie Ellsberry. The enlisted quarters were converted from Officer quarters from way back in WWII. We had a dog Beatrice, who had puppies one hot Summer. We also had a cute calico cat that had an adorable kitten and Ellen broke the cat's heart when she gave away the kitten. The cat would literally search her bedspread looking for the kitten. On several occasions, Ellen and I and the kids would branch out and see the local sights, such as King's Dominion amusement park in northern Virginia, or Washington National Zoo. Boy them rollercoasters and water slides sure were fun!

One couple who were friends to Ellen were SSG Paul Brown and his wife Wanda, both from West Virginia. Paul had a gentle southern accent that ingratiated himself to people in that manner. Ellen had dated a Mexican-American NCO nicknamed 'Pepe' before me, and now and then, he would ask her why she was dating me, saying to her, 'He's too young.' She seemed to ignore him and didn't care. I think I had beaten out Helgenson as well for Ellen's hand, because he tried to cozy up to her a bit as well. Also, Walker was having an affair with Odom's wife, who once told Walker, 'thanks Asshole!' So there was always a possibility of a 'love triangle' in the Army!

Heather had been born at Fort Belvoir, but Ellen had been recently divorced from her 1st husband Doug Ellsberry, so she must have given herself 'the green 'light' to start over in life. Steven, Heather and I got along okay, but Ellen didn't want me to adopt, because that might let Dougie 'off the hook.'

Mills had once just simply walked off the base, going AWOL as a result, and I never ever found out what happened to him after that. Hernandez, another roommate, who was going Special Forces, had a visiting Puerto Rican female Army soldier to our room who had a B.A. degree from a Puerto Rican University. I remember her and her gentle manners. That was popular for Medics- to go Special Forces after one enlistment, not just for SF, but to 'lock in' Jump School.

In fact, during the Combat Engineer ANCOC, an Airborne soldier approached me and recognized me from Fort Benning, Georgia, and he told a fellow soldier, 'I put this newbie out of a C-141!' He had been my Jump Master at Benning and I did indeed recognize him. A Green Beret soldier, observing, said 'Come on over here Airborne!' and as I approached, they were happy to meet the new blood in the Army.

Moton's favorite 'mantra' was 'Goin' to the Field!' or 'Four-Wheelin!' or 'Shammin!' We moaned when we could cruise to the snack bar before or after exercises and grab some quality grub. I would even sneak under a fence at Ft. A.P. Hill while parked at a hidden off-road spot and grab some food from a nearby off-base civilian convenience store. We had one incident when two deuce-and-a-half trucks were roaring in opposite directions and literally crashed into each other in the snow. One soldier was killed during a Pennsylvania National Guard exercise when he leaped out of a truck on a highway and another truck slammed into the back of the vehicle he had just emerged from- fatally striking him. A bad day happened for us, when a bridging accident happened at Belvoir, and a bridge collapsed on soldiers causing serious injuries, unsure if there were fatalities. I remember our female medics just looking bewildered that day who had been through it.

Another incident occurred when a Serbian-American Army NCO, who always emphasized safety, had placed his finger in a bridging girder hole, and then the group accidentally slid the girder, slicing off one of his fingertips, causing immense pain too. He was always telling the soldiers not to place their fingers in the hole when they checked to see if it lined up, but he did just that. Anyway, he came running over to us, and I was half asleep when he came over, shocked by his poor hand. My buddy Walker came out of the back of the rig, and we drove him to the on-base Army Hospital, quickly pulling into the E.R. in reverse. We had the detached end of the finger in ice and brought it to the E.R doctor, with Walker saying, 'Doc, here's the finger,' but the doctor could do little to save the fingertip since it was already detached. All I know is, we lost no time bringing the patient quickly to the E.R.;

Another day there had been an incident in the Motor Pool, when a tire had exploded while some soldiers were working on it, impaling a pencil through the hand of one soldier. I rushed upon the scene with another medic (female), and I instructed her to wrap the wound carefully and not remove the object. Because of my quick action in bringing my aid bag and arriving on scene, Wooden gave me the day off.

One day, during a PT session, under some trees along a jogging path, a 36 year-old Army SSG fell out, had a heart attack, and died. Some said he was a chain smoker and fervent coffee drinker, and that this lifestyle may have contributed to his death. Last taps for the Sarge! Unrelated, One time I was walking near the barracks and another soldier said, 'you should join the Marines!' Not a bad idea. I think he said this because I was always doing pushups.

I also earned my Emergency Medical Technician (EMT) Certificate at Fort Belvoir, Virginia and had rotated through the hospital not only for EMT practicums in the ER

and Labor and Delivery wards, but also helping out on the Medicine Ward and drawing lab specimens for practice. I had two adult twins collapse on me while I was drawing blood but I was able to revive them- that was the kicker, they *both* collapsed. They weren't the only ones who collapsed that day either. Another time, a federal prisoner was brought in DOA from Lorton Prison in Virginia, and a Black Army NCO told me, 'there's a dead man in there, go take a look.' I did and witnessed what looked like a young black man lying on a table that appeared as if he had been in the peak of health, with eyes watery and a stab wound to the neck. Apparently blood loss had killed him. I also treated an Army General with AIDS on the Medicine floor as well as a Marine Captain who was sluggish after surgery, and jibbed me about my 'Evacuare' brass on my whites. His wife really wanted him to pull through and I think he did. I also helped apply a temporary arm splint to a young teenage girl who had a broken arm, almost immediately after she came in, thereby speeding her on her way to recovery.

At the Army Education Center at Belvoir, I CLEP'ed out of many tests through DANTES, literally not having to pay for any of the CLEP tests. This helped accelerate my earning of an A.S. degree in General Studies at Northern Virginia Community College in Woodbridge, Virginia, in August 1987. I was always reading or taking out books at the library, taking correspondence courses, and going to night classes on-base. Earn your degree! Audie Murphy would have been proud!

With Ellen's nudging, I applied for the Army Officer Candidate School (OCS) board, but I think it hurt me that I still had not posted my degree at the time I went before the Board. Also, she misplaced the decorations on my uniform the day before the Board. In any case, the Army Captain said I needed 'more education' and I took this in a positive light. Only 2 out of 7 applicants that cycle were accepted, one a Hispanic female Army SSG and grad of Florida State. Like Plato might say, 'All our hopes are for them, none for ourselves!'

One Winter, it was so cold during a 52 Delta AIT exercise, that I pulled soldier after soldier from their foxholes in the field single-handedly, carefully keeping track of their weapons, and evacuated them to the main Hospital, thereby avoiding frostbite injuries that could have turned into gangrene. I got the requisite permission from the Captain at the site to evacuate them. Good leadership decision, let the medic do his thing!

One time, Niles Arrington and I aided a young civilian woman who had an ankle injury at a Coast Guard event, carefully placing a bandage and 'ice pack' on her ankle. Niles had once gotten jealous of me after his wife Karen had made a pass at me, and not long after, he approached me with a knife in hand, telling me never to go near Karen. I told him I had not approached her and he backed off. We still remained friends. Niles had a son, nicknamed 'butthead', and his wife was diagnosed with brain cancer after they had been stationed in West Germany sometime around the Chernobyl Incident (1986). Niles, Karen, Ellen and I had visited Corpus Christi and South Padre Island sometime when Ellen and I lived in San Antonio.

Ellen had done the paperwork for Nursing School (LPN) while at Belvoir, and she also went to bat for at the Pentagon, with a box of handkerchiefs in hand, to plead to a civil servant lady, to cut me orders so I could be transferred to Ft. Sam Houston, Texas, as well. It worked and they agreed to send me to Texas on the condition that I pay for my own CONUS-to-CONUS travel. She left for Ft. Sam, months before I did,

and I had to room with Garrett and Johnson in the enlisted barracks, with Tracy flirting. Garrett and I would cruise route 1, which bisected the base, in his convertible, and laugh about protecting each other from Johnson, who was gay. Johnson would bring his gay Army friend in on nights or weekends and he would pull a curtain along his side of the room, and I imagine that is how they enjoyed themselves. That was back in the day when a gay lifestyle was illegal in the Army. Those were the days! Johnson didn't like me doing tons of pushups in our room and it got to the point where Roy got involved and couldn't do much, so I eventually told Johnson to 'go cry to the 1st Sgt. about it!'

I saw *Platoon* (1986), starring Charlie Sheen, William Defoe, and Tom Berenger, while stationed at Fort Belvoir, and *Gardens of Stone* (1987), starring James Caan & James Earl Jones, was also filmed at the base while I was there. I was also involved in a photo shoot, where they had a number of Army Medic soldiers, including myself and Nurses, pose in front of a vehicle for high-quality photos for the cover or spread in a magazine. It was done professionally, with an M1010 vehicle and black drape as background.

In one instance, Roy, his white woman, Ellen and I, hung out at Ellen's place, while the woman did a 'strip show' for us, making Roy smile as a result. That didn't stop Roy from having to discipline me at the end of my tour, when I went on sick call, after someone pulled my 'comp time', that I had rightfully earned. They made me salute the flagpole in the morning in 'dress greens' for three straight days, but there was no article 15 or NJP, so I still 'skated.' They also secretly kept tearing down my orders that were posted on the wall for promotion to Specialist-Four, that I had earned. I didn't know where this negativity was coming from, but I proudly put them back up each time. The 1st Sgt. seemed to like me, because I was always scoring high on PT tests and was sort of 'gung ho.' They had offered me my pick of a chance at Air Assault School or the EFMB test, and I thought I did Ok choosing the latter, until I failed the written test at Fort Meade, sort of 'boloing' on my chance to earn the badge.

Upon my PCS to Fort Sam Houston, Texas, in the fall of 1987, a departing remark was made to some soldiers: "Tell Roy to shine his own boots!" Fortunately, this *vituperative* remark was not overheard by anyone else. It served as a fitting conclusion to the time spent at Fort Belvoir, Virginia.